

Studies in Natural and Synthetic Flavonoids. Part III. Synthesis and Stereochemistry of Flavan-4- α -ols

B. L. Verma and M. M. Bokadia

6-Methyl-4'-methoxy- and -3',4'-dimethoxy-flavan-4- α -ols have been prepared by the lead tetra-acetate oxidation of the corresponding flavans which have been obtained in good yields by Clemmensen reduction of the flavanones. The 2,4-*trans* arrangement of substituents in the case of 6-methyl-4'-methoxyflavan-4- α -ol and its acetate has been confirmed by NMR spectra. The 4-hydroxyl and 4-acetoxy groups in these compounds have been shown to have quasi-axial conformation.

Flavan-4-ols (i.e. flavans with a 4-hydroxyl group) are becoming of increasing importance due to their reactivity in polymerisation reactions. Their β -epimers have generally been synthesised either by metal hydride reduction^{1,2} or catalytic hydrogenation³ of the corresponding flavanones. These have been closely studied and much attention has been directed to the configuration and conformation of the 4-hydroxyl group⁴⁻⁵.

Recently, methods have been reported for the stereospecific synthesis of flavan-4- α -ols⁶⁻⁷. Thus Bogner *et al.*³ have reported the synthesis of flavan-4- α -ols by the reaction of nitrous acid on 4-aminoflavan. Their attempts to prepare 6-methyl-4'-methoxyflavan-4- α -ol by this method, however, did not succeed. We have now achieved the stereospecific synthesis of 6-methyl-4'-methoxyflavan-4- α -ol (V) and 6-methyl-3',4'-dimethoxyflavan-4- α -ol (VI) by the lead tetra-acetate oxidation of the corresponding flavans (I & II). But, when this method was applied for the synthesis of 3',4'-dimethoxyflavan-4- α -ol (VII), negative results were obtained. In this case even after prolonged treatment with lead tetra-acetate, the starting material was recovered unchanged.

1. Bogner and Rakosi, *Acta Chim. Acad. Sci. Hung.*, 1967, 13, 217.
2. Kaashikar and Kulkarni, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1969, 18B, 418.
3. Bogner *et al.*, *Tetrahedron*, 1962, 18, 135.
4. Clark Lewis *et al.*, *Proc. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 20.
5. Lillys *et al.*, *Chem. & Ind.*, 1968, 783.
6. Bogner *et al.*, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1969, No. 19, 4.
7. Bokadia *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.* 1960, 3308.

6-Methyl-4'-methoxyflavan (I), 6-methyl-3',4'-dimethoxyflavan (II), and 3',4'-dimethoxyflavan (III), used in these reactions, have been prepared by Clemmensen reduction of the corresponding flavanones in satisfactory yields.

The NMR spectra of flavan-4- α -ol and flavan-4- β -ol benzoates have been studied by Lillya *et al.*⁸ The values for 4- β -epimer ($J_2, 3a + J_2, 3b = 13.7$, $J_{3a,4} + J_{3b,4} = 16.2$ c.p.s.) and 4- α -epimer ($J_2, 3a + J_2, 3b = 14.9$, $J_{3a,4} + J_{3b,4} = 6.0$ c.p.s.) show that flavan-4- β -ols have 2,4-*cis* and flavan-4- α -ols have 2,4-*trans* arrangement. Further, it has been concluded that in flavan-4- β -ol, the 2-phenyl and 4-hydroxyl groups are both equatorial and in flavan-4- α -ol, the 2-phenyl group is equatorial and the 4-hydroxyl group is axial. Thus these observations completely reverse the previous tentative assignment made by Bognar *et al.*⁹

The previous view⁹ that 6-methyl-4'-methoxyflavan-4- α -ol, obtained by lead tetra-acetate oxidation of the corresponding flavan, belongs to 2,4-*trans* series, has been confirmed in this communication by the NMR spectra study of 6-methyl-4'-methoxyflavan-4- α -ol (V) and its acetate. The NMR spectra of 2 and 4 protons of flavan-4- α -ol (VIII) ($J_2, 3a + J_2, 3b = 14.3$, $J_{3a,4} + J_{3b,4} = 5.8$ c.p.s.) and 4- α -ol acetate (IX) ($J_2, 3a + J_2, 3b = 14.3$, $J_{3a,4} + J_{3b,4} = 6.0$ c.p.s.) are similar. Comparison of these values with those described above shows clearly that 6-methyl-4'-methoxyflavan-4- α -ol (VIII) and its acetate (IX) have 2,4-*trans* arrangement of substituents.

It has been shown recently¹⁰ by proton magnetic resonance spectra that the acetoxy group in flavan-3, 4-diol diacetate shows a sharp proton resonance peak, unsplit by spin-spin coupling. Similar peaks have been observed in proton resonance spectra of some acetylated pyranose sugars¹¹. In these, the peaks for axial acetoxy groups always occur at a lower field than those for equatorial acetoxy groups. For pyranose sugars, the values are T_{ax} 7.97-8.13 and T_{eq} 8.13-8.31. Since in flavans the 2-phenyl group is usually equatorial and since the 4- α -ol and its acetate are 2,4-*trans*, the 4-hydroxyl (T 7.41) and 4-acetoxy (T 7.75) are axial. The occurrence of the peaks for these groups at a lower field than for acetylated pyranose sugars is probably a result of the quasi-axial¹² nature of the 4-hydroxyl and 4-acetoxy groups.

EXPERIMENTAL

Lead Tetra-acetate Oxidation of 6-Methyl-4'-methoxyflavan (I)

(a). 2,4-*trans*-6-Methyl-4'-methoxyflavan-4- α -ol (V).—6-Methyl-4'-methoxyflavan^{13,14}

* M.p.s. are uncorrected.

8. *Chem. & Ind.*, 1963, 84.

9. Verma and Bokadia, *Curr. Sci.*, 1964, 33, 648.

10. Bokadia *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 4803.

11. Lemieux *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 79, 1005.

12. Philbin and Wheeler, *Proc. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 167.

13. Bokadia and Verma, *Chem. & Ind.*, 1964, 235.

14. Verma and Bokadia, *ibid.*, 1964, 807.

(1.7 g.), dry benzene (60 ml), and lead tetra-acetate (3.4 g.) were refluxed on a water bath. After 10 hr. the solution showed negative test for quadrivalent lead. It was then filtered and the filtrate was washed with water. The organic layer was separated and dried over anhydrous magnesium sulphate. After removal of the solvent, a yellowish liquid obtained was treated with methanolic potassium hydroxide (MeOH 10 ml; KOH 0.5 g.) and the solution was refluxed for $1\frac{1}{2}$ hr. The reaction product was filtered hot and most of the solvent was removed under suction. The liquid was diluted with water (80 ml) and the solution extracted with ether (3×30 ml). The ethereal extract was dried over anhydrous magnesium sulphate. The liquid obtained after removal of the ether was crystallised from methanol in colorless needles (0.9 g.), m.p. 128-29°. (Found: C, 75.3; H, 6.7. $C_{17}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 75.5; H, 6.6%).

This 4-ol showed in chloroform T 7.41 (axial-OH). Kulkarni *et al.* obtained 6-methyl-4'-methoxyflavan-4-ol, m.p. 127-28°, by aluminium amalgam reduction of the corresponding flavanone.

(b). Acetylation of the compound (0.2 g.) was effected in presence of pyridine and acetic anhydride. The resulting compound furnished shining plates from ethanol, m.p. 110-12°. (Found: C, 72.6; H, 6.8. $C_{19}H_{20}O_4$ requires C, 73.0; H, 6.4%). The acetate in chloroform showed T 7.75 (axial-OAc).

Lead Tetra-acetate Oxidation of 6-Methyl-3',4'-dimethoxyflavan (II)

(i). 6-Methyl-3',4'-dimethoxyflavanone, required, for the preparation of flavan, was prepared in better yields (80.8%) than reported earlier¹⁵ (52%) as follows.

2'-Hydroxy-5'-methyl-3,4-dimethoxychalcone (25 g.) was dissolved in ethanol (300 ml). To this solution H_2SO_4 (conc., 40 ml) was added and it was refluxed on a water bath for 4 hr. When the solution developed a dark red colour, it was left as such overnight. A pale yellow crystalline compound separating was filtered, washed with water, dried, and then crystallised from ethanol in pale yellow flakes (20.2 g.) which became colorless on further crystallisation; m.p. 106-107° (Clarklewis *et al.*'s report m.p. 108-109°).

(ii). 6-Methyl-3',4'-dimethoxyflavan (II).—Zinc amalgam was prepared by taking zinc wool (100 g.), mercuric chloride (10 g.), water (150 ml), and HCl (conc., 5 ml) and shaking the mixture for 5-7 min. The aqueous solution was decanted. The zinc amalgam obtained was first washed with water (3×30 ml) and then with glacial acetic acid (3×10 ml).

To 6-methyl-3',4'-dimethoxyflavanone (12 g.), dissolved in glacial acetic acid (300 ml), zinc amalgam was added, followed by HCl (conc., 36 ml). It was kept for 24 hr. at the room temperature with occasional shaking. The solution was filtered, diluted with water, and kept in a refrigerator overnight. The reddish coloured solid separating was filtered, washed with water, and dried. It was crystallised from methanol in colorless prisms (8.7 g.), m.p. 79-80°. (Found: C, 75.7; H, 7.2. $C_{18}H_{20}O_3$ requires C, 76.0; H, 7.0%).

(iii). 2,4-trans-6-Methyl-3',4'-dimethoxyflavan-4- α -ol (VI).—To the preceding flavan (II) (3 g.), dissolved in dry benzene (120 ml), lead tetra-acetate (10 g.) was added and the solution was refluxed on a water bath for 12 hr. when it showed negative quadrivalent lead test with starch iodide paper. It was treated in the usual manner to yield a yellowish viscous liquid. The liquid was hydrolysed with methanolic KOH (5%, 20 ml) by refluxing on a water bath for 2 hr. The product was worked up as in the previous case to afford a yellowish liquid which was crystallised from benzene in colorless globules, m.p. 120-22°. Recrystallisation from methanol furnished colorless needles (1.2 g.), m.p. 134°. (Found: C, 71.7; H, 6.2. $C_{18}H_{20}O_4$ requires C, 72.0; H, 6.6%).

(iv). Acetylation of the above compound (0.3 g.) in presence of pyridine and acetic anhydride afforded a colorless solid, crystallising from ethanol in colorless silky needles (0.2 g.), m.p. 103-104°. (Found: C, 69.7; H, 6.6. $C_{20}H_{22}O_3$ requires C, 70.1; H, 6.4%).

Lead Tetra-acetate Oxidation of 3',4'-Dimethoxyflavan (III)

(a). 3',4'-Dimethoxyflavan.—To 3',4'-dimethoxyflavanone¹⁶ (12 g.), dissolved in glacial acetic acid (300 ml), zinc amalgam was added, followed by HCl (conc., 36 ml). The mixture was kept at the room temperature for 24 hr. with occasional shaking and worked up as in (II). The compound, thus obtained, furnished colorless prisms (7.4 g.) from methanol, m.p. 98-99° (lit.¹⁷ m.p. 99.5-100.5°; lit.¹⁸ m.p. 99-100°). (Found: C, 75.3; H, 6.5. Calc. for $C_{17}H_{18}O_3$: C, 75.5; H, 6.7%).

(b). Attempted Synthesis of 2,4-trans-3',4'-Dimethoxyflavan-4- α -ol (VII).—The oxidation of 3',4'-dimethoxyflavan with lead tetra-acetate was tried in the usual manner. After hydrolysis of the intermediate acetoxy compound, a reddish liquid was obtained in low yield, from which the starting compound was recovered unchanged. Increase in reaction period (24 hr.) and use of excess of lead tetra-acetate (5 moles) had no effect.

The authors express their sincere thanks to Dr. D. G. Roux, Chief Research Scientist, Leather Industries Research Institute, Grahamstown, South Africa, for the NMR spectra and Prof. T. R. Seshadri, F.R.S., Delhi University, for the micro-analytical values of some of the compounds. The authors are also grateful to Dr. W. V. Bhagwat, D.Sc., Prof. and Head, School of Studies in Chemistry, Vikram University, Ujjain, for laboratory facilities and the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, New Delhi, for the fellowship to one of them (B.L.V.).

SCHOOL OF STUDIES IN CHEMISTRY,
VIKRAM UNIVERSITY,
UJJAIN, M.P.

Received June 4, 1965.

16. Hattori, *Bull. Chem. Soc., Japan*, 1927, 2, 171

17. Bokadia *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.* 1962, 1958.

18. Hathway and Seakins, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 1562.